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CLIMATE CHANGE ADAPTATION AND CHALLENGES TO SUSTAINABLE LIVELIHOODS IN THE NIGER DELTA

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ABSTRACT: *The issue of climate change is one of the most important global issues of the 21st century making it a front-burner on major global discourse. While Nigeria before this time was rarely affected by climate change-induced natural disasters, recent events have however shown that the country is not immune to this. To this end, there is a growing concern about the need to reduce human activities that threaten the environment. Despite this growing concern, the Multinational Oil Corporations operating in the Niger Delta has continued to engage in the most devastating environmentally damaging activities coupled with the weak regulatory frameworks. The major objective of this work is to investigate the link between climate change adaptation and the challenges to sustainable livelihoods in the Niger Delta. Using the triangulation and process tracing method the paper argued that while the extractive companies and artisanal oil refining activities of local communities undermine environmental sustainability, livelihood adaptation measures differ in different context particularly artisanal refining as a strategy. The research indicates artisanal oil refining cannot be cauterized as adaptation strategy like other agro based strategies as this is more of a 'protest strategy evolving from years of frustration and discontent with the oil companies. However, this protest strategy as an attempt to address seeming loss of livelihoods has further thrown local communities further into the poverty trap. The paper notes that there is need to develop appropriate strategies in extenuating the impacts of climate change on the environment. Thus, the paper suggests that an environmental state of emergency be declared in the Niger Delta before the situation gets out of hand.*

Keywords: *Climate Change, Adaptation, and Sustainable Livelihoods.*

Introduction

The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) Fourth Assessment Report 2007 established that global climate change is already happening. It warned that communities who live in marginal lands and whose livelihoods are highly nature-dependent could be among the most vulnerable (IPCC, 2007). The full impacts of climate change on many

ecological environments are evolving, however, what has been established is that significant dependence on nature-based livelihoods sources are more susceptible to its vagaries (Zibima, 2015; African Development Bank, 2003; Burton et al., 2002).

The Niger Delta region possesses a unique characteristic as the largest wetland in the

world covering an area of 70,000 square kilometers and described as sandy coastal ridge barriers of brackish or saline mangroves. The region is further characterized by freshwater and Permanent seasonal swamp forests as well as lowlands. It is traversed by a substantial number of rivulets, streams, canals, and creeks ((NDDC, 2006)). Geographically, the Niger Delta consists of areas identified with deltaic characteristics in the southern part of Nigeria which include Bayelsa, Rivers, and Delta State) and parts of Akwa Ibom, Cross River, Edo and Ondo states (Okoko and Ibaba, 1997). Although, under the characterization as oil-producing, the Niger Development Commission (NDDC) broadened this to nine states to include even Abia and Imo States (NDDC, 2001). It is the hub of oil and gas production accounting for over 80 percent of export earnings and 90 percent of GDP (Ibaba, 2017; Statista, 2020). Like most sectors, the oil industry is dominated by multinational corporations (MNOCs) such as Chevron, SPDC etc. with over 600 oil fields (5,284 Onshore and Offshore oil wells exploring oil and gas resources degrading the environment (Lubeck, Watts, and Lipschutz, 2007)). Scholars agree that the most pervasive cause of environmental degradation in the Niger Delta has been the unguarded exploration activities of MNOCs without diminishing the place of other activities by locals such as bush burning, petroleum fires, artisanal oil refining, indiscriminate waste disposal, excessive balkanization of land and others ((Jike, 2004)). However, it must be said that in comparison with the activities of MNOCs, this is insignificant.

The commercialization of oil in 1958 and subsequent exploitation activities of MNOCs came with it environmental degradation emboldened by weak

regulatory framework. Previous studies on the link between climate change adaptation and sustainable livelihoods focused on the assumed use of traditional adaptation measures (Ibaba, 2015; Zibima, 2015; Efe, 2010). Others focus on the analysis of climatic change, the adaptation and mitigation measures, and the factors precipitating livelihood insecurity in the region (Uyigue and Agho, 2007; Onakuse and Lenihan, 2008; Onwuemele and Olorumfemi, 2010), ignoring the differential nuances in adaptation measures from one community to the other and the mutual and self-reinforcing relationship between some aspects of livelihood adaptations and climate change and vice versa. The objective of this study therefore was to interrogate the linkage between climate change adaptation and sustainable livelihood challenges in 9 study communities in Bayelsa state.

To do this, we employed the case study method combined with desk-based research in both upland and riverine/coastal communities in Bayelsa to provide a fair basis for comparison of adaptation measures. This is imperative because there is a significant need for community-specific data as the generic/broad assumptions on livelihood adaptation defies the importance of specificities. The paper is divided into 4 main parts. The first deals with the theoretical literature followed by theoretical foundation. The other sections deal the methodology employed in the research and key arguments/conclusions drawn.

The Niger Delta and the Impact of Climate Change

It is no news that exploitation activities of MNOCs have overtime degraded the environment. Incessant spills, gas flare and other acts pollute the air, and water, destroying flora and fauna. The flaring of

gas has pushed hydrocarbon into the air leading to rising temperature and the evaporation of water bodies (rivers and Oceans which ultimately leads to heavy rainfall and the floods that follow. For instance, Udosen (2008) reports that between 1977-2005, the annual rainfall in Akwa Ibom State was high as 2443.3mm-an indication of heavy rainfall in the region and the coastal Niger Delta is even worse. Efe (2010), noted that rainfall distribution over the past one hundred years in the Niger Delta region experienced 2901mm annual rainfall.

Flooding as one of the effects has destroyed properties, farmlands crops and the disruption of agricultural activities forcing local farmers to seek new livelihood strategies dubbed-adaptation strategies. The 2012 floods for instance in the Niger Delta submerged farmlands, destroying crops and rendering communities homeless and locals hungry. Cultivated crops were destroyed with serious leaching leading to loss of soil fertility. Similarly, water sources were contaminated long contamination of underground water by hydrocarbon pollution. These cause serious health and respiratory problems (Uchegbu, 1998). In the end, local communities incur losses as they are unable to mobilize resources for the next planting season haven lost all in the floods.

Climate Change (CC) Adaptation and Sustainable Livelihoods: The Literature

The literature on the link between climate adaptation and sustainable livelihoods is categorized into 2 strands. A strand of the literature (Ibaba, 2015; Ikelegbe, 2005) argues that climate change undermines existing livelihood sources and by implication negatively impacts livelihoods. It further notes that the oil industry activities degrade the environment leading

to the destruction of livelihoods and worsening prevailing environmental conditions contributing to a decline in productivity, and occupational displacement (UNDP 2006; Opukri and Ibaba, 2008; Obi, 2009). To these they recommend livelihood adaptation options largely agro based. These include mixed cropping, cultivation of early maturing varieties, early cropping, construction of dykes etc including greater awareness creation, education on best adaptation methods.

A study conducted in Osun Southwest Nigeria concluded that adaptation strategies often include crop rotation, mixed cropping practices, and the use of water channels as draining systems, mulching, regular weeding, and conservation of soil moisture through appropriate tilling (Okoroh, et' al, 2016). Others such as (Allison, 2015; Zibima, 2015; Ikelegbe, 2005) indicate an established adaptation measure in the Niger Delta is artisanal oil refining developed in response to the loss of their livelihoods caused by activities of MNOCs.

The theorized linkage between climate change and adaptation appears to be a one-way thread. That is, unguarded activities of MNOCs in addition to human activities have affected the weather pattern which in turn affect the nature-based livelihoods of locals within communities. Therefore, to address this trend, livelihood adaptation options have often been suggested around both agro based (early cropping, etc) or social based strategies focused on increased community decision making in adaptation planning, climate-resilient agriculture, and transparent and robust socio-cultural and ecological assessment of vulnerability coping (Centre for Population and Environmental Development (CPED, 2020). This is based on an understanding

that these strategies can build adaptive capacities to enable people to cope better with change and diversity and a realization that different stakeholders are affected differently and possess different capacities to adapt depending on their access to capital (Carr, 2008; Ziervogel et al., 2006). Yet the other strand note that livelihood adaptation options mirror the available natural conditions within given contexts (Zibima, 2015; Allison and Akintola, 2015). Here, the livelihood adaptation choices of local communities range from agricultural cultivation, fishing, farming particularly around early cropping, shifting cultivation, use of early maturing plants, etc (Ibaba, 2009). While the literature provides a lot of hindsight on the critical impact, there is a broad conception within this that climate change adaptation and livelihood options are the same across communities, beyond this that existing livelihood sources are also adaptation measures.

Urdal (2006) cautions that considerable uncertainties exist concerning the extent and geographical distribution of these changes (adaptation) and by implication the adaptation measures. Predicting scenarios for how climate-related environmental change may influence human societies and political systems necessarily involves an even higher degree of uncertainty. The paper argues that while there are similar CC challenges and livelihood adaptation measures from different contexts, the peculiar natural environments cum socio-economic conditions within local communities define the CC challenges and livelihood adaptation choices of local communities

whether sustainable or not inversely affect sustainable exploitation of agricultural resources within these communities. While there is a significant push all around for adaptation to be better placed, there is a need to separate deliberate adaptation from protest livelihood alternatives which do not fall under this gamut and a clear understanding of the different adaptation nuances in different communities is key.

Conceptual Framework

The sustainable livelihoods framework (SLF) is particularly relevant to understand the focus of the paper because it provides a basis for analyzing both the key components that makeup livelihoods and the contextual factors that influence them (Reed, 2013). The Sustainable Livelihood Framework (SLF) exemplifies circumstances in which actors strategically rely on available resources within their locale to forge livelihood adaptation (Parkinson and Ramirez 2007). It highlights the factors that affect livelihood, their variable importance, and how they interact (DFID, 2001). The significance of the SLF lies in its identification of the relationship elements within and around the context of an individual and the material and human networks that exist upon which the actors rely on to influence and in turn shape his livelihood choices notwithstanding what those choices become. The SLF muses' factors influencing the choice of adaptations and potential trade-offs between adaptation options.

Figure 1. Sustainable Livelihoods Framework (SLF)

Sustainable-livelihoods-framework (DFID-2001, p. 2).

As depicted above, the environment within which livelihood options exist are both human and material in nature. Therefore, adaptation decisions made is a function of the interactional elements that influence livelihood in the context. The first-natural environment highlights threats to the environment both natural and man-made and the condition of naturally occurring structures like rivers, forests and weather. These have influences on the likely shock to livelihood and the trend. The second component- the human perspective on livelihood outcomes notes the direct activities and capabilities of the person and the available resources that can be relied on. These include both human capacity (skills sets, individual/households), natural capital (land, rivers, oceans, etc), financial capital (poverty, income, etc), social capital (information/interaction networks, trust, bonds, friendship/family, etc.) and physical capital (availability/accessibility of assets for generating income. The third

strand talks about institutional effectiveness and policy outcomes. These include issues in the regulatory environment, policies on access to resources in the environment. These also define adaptation outcomes about people's response to climate change and environmental shocks.

Interestingly the institutional context looping back to the vulnerability context signifies the point human actions that result in livelihoods function mostly within conditions/forces set by the environmental variability and institutional effectiveness. Therefore, livelihood outcomes are influenced by the interface between existing vulnerabilities and the policy context, in addition to the role of individuals in the process play. The point to note is that livelihood adaptation strategies and the challenges are a product of the natural environment and policy direction of the system, it is also the perspective, capabilities, and choices of the individual relying on such strategies (Parkinson & Ramirez, 2006). Flowing from these, livelihood adaptation strategy and challenges across local communities

is a function of the existing dynamics/context within these communities. This is influenced by existing knowledge of leadership structures and community. Therefore, existing livelihood adaptation strategies employed by local communities are a function of the resources available within that environment which on one hand is a reactionary economic alternative by locals against MNOCs and a reaction to the destruction of erstwhile existing arable land due to oil. In this, the task of the authors is to assess the contextual dynamics of climate change adaptation and livelihood challenges across communities in Bayelsa state and the Niger Delta to situate the linkage. Therefore, adaptation is contextualized and artisanal refining is a product of deliberate action influenced by the capabilities of locals. Clearly, artisanal oil refining is more of a protest economic activity than a coping mechanism (Rufus, 2019).

As employed in the study, Climate change (CC) seen as variation in the earth's global or regional climate over time due to the variability or anthropogenic factors caused by significant concentrations of greenhouse gases (GHG). Adaptation on the other hand refers to deliberate actions taken to aid communities and ecologies moderate, cope with or take advantage of expected changes in climate conditions (USAID, 2009). Adaptation aims to build/strengthen resilience to reduce vulnerability either anticipatory or reactive. A key part of the anticipatory strategy is the use of more sustainable livelihood strategies drawn from the locale of communities.

Methodology

The case study qualitative research technique was utilized in this study. On this, 27 Key Informant interviews, cutting across community chiefs, women, youths,

and others from 9 communities were conducted purposively. Communities selection was based on history of oil production and social/environmental conflicts. Size and population of community was a key factor in the number of interviews per community. The number of interviews was purposive-determined by time and resources available to the researcher following the rules of case studies of this nature.

Figure 1. Interviews Distribution across 9 communities

Source: Fieldwork data (2020).

Climate Change Coping/Adaptation Strategies in Bayelsa State

Aggregate data indicate that 16% of all respondents (56) fall within the age brackets of 18-24 while those between 25-34 make up 41% (140) of all respondents. Similarly, the respondents between the age bracket of 35-49 make up a substantial 30% of all respondents while those above the age of 50 years make up just 13% of all respondents. In the same vein, 7.9% of respondents are secondary school students while undergraduates make up 13% of all respondents. Significant also is the percentage of unemployed respondents (22%) and indeed 24.6% of respondents who represent every day local farmers and fishermen/women in the 9 OPCs in Bayelsa state. The study communities lie within the flat and low belt of Bayelsa state either as upland or riverine. However, a common thread across all is

their position as oil-producing communities (OPC all suffering in various degrees' environmental degradation. In the upland communities of Kalaba, Otuasega, Akumoni, and Ikarama the vagaries of Climate Change (CC) can be visibly seen the annual flooding across these communities leading to the destruction of farmlands, displacement of locals, and the destruction of properties, crops, and the livelihood of the community. At the point of writing this, the identified communities have been significantly submerged in water following the now regular annual floods in the state. Livelihood adaption/coping strategies across the identified communities ranged from early cropping, change from capture fishing to a lot of culture, early harvest amongst others. As a community leader of Kalaba highlighted during an interview:

Livelihoods have been affected adversely over the years, most persons are no longer interested in farming, due to oil pollution of water and land, many took to

white-collar jobs.

Other adaptation strategies include the change of occupation with a lot of respondents noting this as a key strategy they have employed over time. However, the specific adaptation dynamics across communities is influenced by other factors. These include education, gender, relationship with the oil company and level of access, nature of community leadership, and location of community vis-a-vis existing oil resources and conflict. While traditional adaptation and livelihood sources have been adopted there are salient nuances from one community to the other. For instance, the study indicates that the harvesting of water snail as a strategy is a predominant strategy in the riverine areas of the study communities. Yet, this does not take place in all identified riverine communities. Livelihood adaptation strategy is a function of the capabilities of local communities defined in terms of the environment, physical and mental capacities to harness nature. These ultimately have implications for the potential effects of CC in these localities and by implication livelihood adaptation strategy.

Artisanal Refining and Climate Change Adaption

Artisanal refineries while noted as a coping/adaptation strategy is borne out of the destruction of the traditional livelihoods in Oil Producing Communities(OPCs), I argue that this livelihood alternative is not necessarily a product of necessity borne out of the destruction of their livelihoods, rather it is a protest livelihood- reaction out of the fractured relationship between corporate practice and local communities and bears little connection at least in the minds of locals as a strategy that was developed simply due to the destruction of local

economies or climate change as the literature notes. The key reason for these lies in the attitude to farming in local communities- youths often see farming as an activity for the aged and poor with what they consider as a low turnover and therefore low profitability. The implication is that mostly the aged are involved in farming in local communities which has been a structural issue within the Delta even before the emergence and commercialization of oil. It must be noted that oil has heightened this attitude and increased the premium on oil. As cited by an Igbomatoru community leader:

Bunkering came to be as a result of the reaction. Action gives rights to a reaction. Because of the way AGIP was relating with community-refusing to implement GMOU, the bunkering was a reprisal attack on Agip. Initially, they just blow up the pipeline as upon know we have a major pipeline/trunk line that carries crude to the international community. So the pipelines were blown up by the community as a reprisal of AGIP's poor handling of the agreement it had with the community- its refusal to implement the agreement reached with the community.

The frosty relationship between MNOCs and communities started from the early 1990s when the Ogonis, Ijaws, Isoko's, and other ethnic groups took matters into their hands the following clampdown by the government. A strategy of occupying and shutting down oil production activities in addition to the abduction of MNOC staff and mass mobilization by youths, women, and other community leaders over the unguarded exploitation of their environment and consequent destruction of its livelihoods gained

momentum (Ikelegbe, 2005, 2009). The objective was clear, 'if they do not benefit from the oil output, then they will stop the oil from being produced' (Arnold 2000: 224). Bunkering described by the Nigerian state as illegal oil refining is the current phase of the process with youths and other community members tapping into MNOC pipelines and refining crude into PMS, kerosene, and diesel for commercial purposes.

My boat was loading 200 drums when the military appeared and razed them down. They also burnt my 20 ovens and emptied my diesel... Since then, it has been difficult to feed and support my children, most especially my 11-year old girl that is blind. Presently, I am picking periwinkle and sea snail to raise little money to run my home. A female ex-artisanal oil refiner.

As shared by O'Brien and Leichenko, (2000), livelihood adaptations are not isolated from other decisions. These can be influenced by the context of demographic, cultural, and economic change as well as transformations in information technologies. It can therefore be difficult to separate climate change adaptation decisions or actions from actions triggered by other social or economic events for which relative deprivation, frustration, and aggression play key roles in the seeming adaptation decision of local oil-bearing communities. More importantly, artisanal oil refining from the field findings was not initiated simply as a deliberate livelihood adaptation approach, rather, it was initiated as an aggressive reaction from the relationship between MNOCs and local communities as is the case with the activities of illegal oil refiners in Igbomatoru. Research published by SDN

(2018) notes the increasing profitability of the illegal trade is a key motivation for youth involvement with camp profitability tripling. Similarly, the rate of return on investment compared to the local and national formal economy has also increased with production efficiency in the refining process increased from 45 to 88 percent in Bayelsa state. These results indicate an increase in refining across local communities where MNOCs operate.

The point to make here is that, while artisanal oil refining has been highlighted as an adaptation measure, results indicate beyond these, that adaptation measure appears to be very profitable and therefore profitability, as highlighted, remains the driving factor influencing illegal refining as an adaptation strategy. In this, the choice of this alternative is not simply borne out some deliberate thought as a climate adaptation process owing to the destruction of their environment. More than anything, the destruction of livelihoods of local communities provided fodder for the implementation of a justifiable protest livelihood attempt to also benefit from the juicy oil industry. In the end, the chosen adaptation area further undermines environmental sustainability worsening poverty in the same communities. The artisanal oil refining economy emerged as a product of the broader natural environment. The illegal refining activities while a coping/adaption strategy further underdevelops local communities as it worsens the environmental challenges through the destruction of flora and fauna through its spills, bush burning, indiscriminate logging of fuel wood, pollution of streams, and other implications.

Agro and Non-Agro Based Adaptation strategies and their Implications.

The economic dynamics of communities are largely agro-based. From the natural ecological environment characterized by streams, vegetation, and other naturally occurring features, agriculture has been the mainstay of local economies. However, there are nuances on the various livelihood adaptation measures across communities with varying degrees of impact. In the riverine areas of Southern Ijaw, livelihood adaptation measures center around specific efforts on early planting and cultivation of crops and the deliberate use of an early maturing variety of crops to ensure early maturation and cultivation. Fast-maturing varieties of maize with high yields have been introduced and are being used by farmers. The risk involved in this strategy is that local species appear to be displaced by these species, even though local varieties are still cultivated.

The risk, however, is that this could undermine sustainable development particularly the extinction of traditional hybrids and the implications therein (Uyigie and Aghe, 2007). Yet again indigenous land husbandry practices specifically around traditional methods of land allocation and cultivation particularly in mountainous areas to reduce the access by floods. In Igbomatoru for instance livelihood adaptation measures have meant the reactivation of rice cultivation in the community to allow for early harvests during the year. This agricultural revolution provides a key livelihood adaptation measure indigenously driven from the community in partnership with development organizations. The cultivation is a key adaptation measure and is strategically interlinked within the weather patterns of the local communities during periods of high and low tides.

As highlighted by Uyigie and Agho, 2007) over 50% of consumed fish in Nigeria

come from the Niger Delta. The adaptation process has seen locals change from natural sources of catching fishing now to the culturing of fish. This is to compensate for the vagaries of the weather in the natural environment where loss is certain. Often it is common to see the change from earthen ponds to culturing using plastic drums and others to culture fish. Similar, change to public service jobs has seen a huge outflow of locals to the city center for better-paying jobs leading to massive rural-urban drifts. Agriculture and other agro-based adaptation measures have been left largely in the hands of the aged contributing to low food production and reinforcing poverty in the communities. Thus, while artisanal refining and other associated strategies are adopted to improve the economic wellbeing of the community, the resultant oil spills, incomplete combustion pollute remaining arable land, waters destroying both flora and fauna and indeed decrease in soil nutrient. In the end, these efforts further deepen the poverty of local communities.

Challenges to Sustainable Livelihood Structures ***Policy Failure***

The operations of the oil companies are supposedly regulated by existing Nigerian laws. Within these, the 1969 Petroleum Decree for instance, reposed ownership of petroleum in the Nigerian state with the Nigerian National Petroleum Corporation tasked with the responsibility of regulating the sector on behalf of the state. Part of this stipulated that 40% equity in all foreign companies had to be owned by Nigerians, and barred foreign companies of a particular size from operating in particular sectors of the economy, notably domestic transport and land ownership (Williams, 1976)). Through this, the NNPC established joint-venture

agreements with MNOCs, on a 40–60% stake with even the 2008 Petroleum Industry Bill and others attempting to increase government hold on the sector. However, years of exploration weak regulatory frameworks occasioned by state failure, corruption has permitted the almost unhindered operations of the MNOCs who in often cases have become 'the government in oil-bearing communities (Nwajiaku-Dahou, 2012). Unguarded oil exploitation activities affect the erstwhile traditional livelihood of local communities rendering community lands, degraded, desolate, and dangerous to farm creating an army of unemployed youths. The existence of oil exploration in Niger Delta has affected the traditional livelihood of the communities often from oil spills which destroy the land, water, and other livelihood sources, and gas flare which impacts both breaths of air, agriculture, water, and human health. These contradictions have created an economy of conflict (Ikelegbe, 2005) a situation characterized by intense violent and bloody confrontations for the control of benefits from the oil economy (Ikelegbe, 2005)). This situation leads to a situation highlighted by Arnold, 'if they do not benefit from the oil output, then they will stop the oil from being produced' (2000: 224). For instance, a massive oil spill from a Nigerian Agip Oil Company (NAOCO facility in 2010 in Igbomatoru led to the destruction of the livelihood of local communities leading to several environmental challenges in the community. These were key trigger factors according to respondents for the alteration of the traditional livelihood of locale and decision to go into bunkering.

The resource curse thesis and associated theoretical standpoints have established the interlink between natural resource-rich countries and poverty and violent

conflicts with the Niger at the top of this discourse. Beyond overdependence on a single resource and lack of diversification, keenly highlighted is the undermining of other key sectors such as agriculture to stimulate innovation and development. Beyond these, in the Niger Delta, the research indicates that some of the challenges of activities of both international oil companies and local refiners is the reduction of crop yield and fish. Other challenges with sustainable adaptation structures are discussed below. Crop yield Reduction- The reduction of crop yield as a result of the spill was a common thread across all study communities. As shared by a female interviewee: Beyond crop quantity and quality reduction, the capture of fish has also severely suffered owing to the largely polluted waters across communities. Adaptation measures although utilized, the output is often limited when compared with the natural environment. Although these disproportionately affect gender differently, because women make up a large proportion of the farming population, the challenges to livelihoods agricultural are often dire. This reduces the capacity of women to meet household needs and often to cope with these shortfalls, unsustainable practices such as the use of dangerous chemicals for catching fish and involvement in illegal oil bunkering becomes the order of the day particularly in some of our study communities. This further undermines environmental sustainability-worsening their dependence and poverty. This finding is supported by a recently published research by SDN (2018) on dirty fuels in the Niger Delta. Among other things, the research highlights that illegal refining practices pollute the environment across local communities, produce low-quality fuel which releases emissions into the atmosphere poisoning

the air. The soot in Port Harcourt for instance has been attributed in part to these activities and the unsustainable manner of destroying products by security agencies tasked with the responsibility of protecting oil infrastructure.

Supporting this dangerous trend, a community member notes that:

Refining practices pollute, and the low-quality fuel produced releases more emissions when consumed. Security agencies burn what they find at our site, or pour it out onto land and waterways. So far a silent hazard, the soot plaguing Port Harcourt over the last two years is expected to be a direct result.

These impact the health and wellbeing of inhabitants, significantly also affecting water availability across local communities. Findings from the field typify the point with sour and polluted water flowing in Igbomatoru community which is the only source of water available to most of these communities besides the burying of sachet weather which is a challenge to most communities. Locals fetch the same water for drinking, cooking, and another purpose with serious health implications. The research indicates that while the artisanal refining in Igbomatoru for instance saw increased profitability throughout 2008-2012, the occupation hazards particularly the economic loss of arable land deep in the first was humongous. In the end, while the activities of MNOCs lead to the degradation of the environment, the adopted coping strategy of local communities worsens their poverty and undermines sustainable development.

Conclusion

The study found that farmers have adopted a broad range of strategies to address climate change. The variation in the type of strategies adopted includes

differences in access to capital, information on the use of different climate change adaptation strategies, and the type of arable crop grown by the individual farmers. These adaptation strategies as highlighted by researchers presuppose some level of understanding of the impacts of climate change and deliberate learning to adapt relying on ones understanding of the context.

By implication, climate change/environmental degradation proceeded climate change and by extension adaptation measures. The paper submits that adaptation is a deliberate process often engaged in to counteract the impacts of environmental degradation caused by extractives, then illegal refining cannot be argued as a climate adaptation approach in the sense of climate adaptation. That is, artisanal oil refining cannot be grouped under this categorization as an adaptation measure following these rules due to its livelihood wrecking and environmentally unsustainable nature. Artisanal refining is a necessary coping strategy borne out of the years of frustration and aggression, however, it is not necessarily an adaptation strategy. The major objective of this study was to investigate the link between climate change adaptation and the challenges to sustainable livelihoods in the Niger Delta. Our findings indicated important relationships between certain rational choices on adaptation and the implications for sustainable development and poverty in local communities. While the agro-based adaptation strategies often lead to some improvement in yield and food crops, illegal refining undermines and worsens the environmental woes throwing local communities further into the vicious cycle of poverty-reinforcing their disempowerment.

The Way Forward

The research indicates that artisanal oil refining is less of a learned/deliberate adaptation measure to counteract climate change, it is rather a protest attempt at the appropriation of benefits from the industry. The implication of these on sustainable livelihoods has further undermined the environment they depend on. In this, the impact of climate change has often been felt more by these areas in the form of flooding and consequent loss of agricultural products, property, and other more severe impacts. The findings demonstrate that an alternative approach is needed to tackle climate change and specifically artisanal oil refining in the region- declaring an emergency may be a first step to addressing the issues. Key to these would include:

- I. Strengthening of the community host section of the petroleum industry bill to protect local communities from unguarded exploitation by MNOCs and the increased participation/stake in the sector.
- II. Develop more sustainable livelihood alternatives by working closely with those involved in the artisanal oil refining business to develop more sustainable models including the modular refinery options.
- III. There is a need for government to strengthen environmental provisions to address peculiar climate challenges of local communities in the region- specifically by increased regulation of the exploration activities of MNOCs particularly in hard-to-reach riverine/coastal communities.

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